

Supporting Information

**Cationic Ring-Opening Polymerization-Induced Self-Assembly
(CROPISA) of 2-Oxazolines: From Block Copolymers to One-Step
Gradient Copolymer Nanoparticles**

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Supplementary information

Cationic ring-opening polymerization-induced self-assembly (CROPISA) of 2-oxazolines: From block copolymers to one-step gradient copolymer nanoparticles

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1. Experimental section

1.1. Materials

2-Phenyl-2-oxazoline (PhOx) was purchased from Sigma Aldrich, distilled from barium oxide, and stored under argon. 2-(3-Ethylheptyl)-2-oxazoline (EHOx) was prepared following a protocol reported in the literature for the synthesis of 2-alkyl-2-oxazolines,^[46] distilled over barium oxide and stored under argon. Anhydrous acetonitrile and dodecane, supplied with molecular sieves under nitrogen atmosphere (AcroSeal by Across), were used as received. Methyl *p*-toluenesulfonate (MeOTs) was purchased from Sigma Aldrich and used as received. All other chemicals were purchased from Sigma-Aldrich unless stated otherwise.

1.2. Synthesis of PEHOx-PPhOx copolymer nanoparticles via CROPISA

A one-pot, two-step protocol was employed for the synthesis of the block copolymers (**Scheme 1**). Several batches of block copolymer nanoparticles were synthesized, with each batch characterized by the same degree of polymerization of the first block (DP₁) and total solid weight percentage (w/w %) but different degrees of polymerization of the second block (DP₂).

As a representative example, for the synthesis of the PEHOx₂₀-*b*-PPhOx_y at 25 w/w %, MeOTs (25 μ L), dodecane (1.4 mL), and EHOx (0.6 mL) were transferred under an argon atmosphere to septum-sealed microwave vials with magnetic stirrers and mixed. The vials were heated to 110 °C, and the polymerization was stopped after 1 hour by cooling down the vial to room temperature. The full conversion of EHOx was confirmed by ¹H NMR spectroscopy, and the crude polymerization mixture was split into 4 aliquots (0.4 mL) that were transferred into 4 different microwave vials under an argon atmosphere. Each microwave vial was filled with a calculated amount of PhOx (0.10-0.21 mL) according to the targeted DP₂ (30-55). Finally, a calculated volume of dodecane (0.6-1.1 mL) was added to adjust the final concentration of polymer to 25 w/w %. The polymerization of the second block was performed at 140 °C for different times (75-120 min) depending on the targeted DP₂. The polymerization mixture was cooled down to room temperature, and the conversion of PhOx was determined by ¹H NMR spectroscopy.

A similar procedure was employed for the gradient copolymer nanoparticles, with the difference that EHOx and PhOx were both added at the start in the polymerization vials, and the polymerization was performed at 140 °C in a one-step, one-pot protocol (**Scheme 2**).

1.3.Characterization of copolymers and copolymer nanoparticles

Size exclusion chromatography (SEC) was used to determine the molar masses (M_w - weight-averaged molar mass, M_n - number-averaged molar mass) and dispersity ($\mathcal{D} = M_w/M_n$) of the polymers using a Malvern Omnisec system, equipped with OMNISEC RESOLVE and OMNISEC REVEAL modules, including an autosampler, a differential refractive index detector, a viscometer and a diode-array-based UV/Vis spectrometer. The separation was performed on two PLgel 5 μm mixed-D columns in a series thermostatted at 55°C in *N,N*-dimethylacetamide (DMAc) containing 50 mM of LiCl at an elution rate of 0.5 mL min⁻¹. Molar masses and dispersities were calculated against narrow-dispersity poly(methyl methacrylate) standards.

Nuclear magnetic resonance (NMR) spectra were measured on a Bruker Advance MSL 400 MHz NMR spectrometer at room temperature in CDCl₃ or CD₂Cl₂. All chemical shifts are expressed as ppm relative to residual solvent signals. The NMR spectra were processed using MestReNova 14.1 software.

Gas chromatography (GC) was used to monitor the CROP kinetics using a GC system (Nexis GC-2030, Shimadzu, Japan) equipped with an FID detector and a Shimadzu SH-5MS column 30 m in length and 0.32 mm in diameter. The inlet temperature was set to 250 °C with a 25:1 split ratio, and hydrogen was used as a carrier gas at a 1.8 mL min⁻¹ flow rate.

Dynamic light scattering (DLS) was used to determine the hydrodynamic diameter of the copolymer nanoparticles using a ZEN3600 Zetasizer Nano-ZS analyzer (Malvern Instruments, UK). Each final polymerization crude sample was diluted in dodecane to a final concentration of 5 mg mL⁻¹. The apparent hydrodynamic diameter of the nanoparticles (D_h) and their polydispersity index (PDI) were determined at a scattering angle of $\theta = 173^\circ$. The data were analyzed using the DTS (Nano) program.

Small-Angle X-ray Scattering (SAXS) experiments were performed at the BIOCEV center (Vestec, Czech Republic) with a SAXSpoint 2.0 instrument (Anton Paar, Graz, Austria) equipped with an Excillum MetalJet C2 X-ray source and with an Eiger R 1M detector (Dectris, Baden-Daettwil, Switzerland). The active area of the detector and the pixel size were 79.9 mm \times 77.2 mm and 75 μm \times 75 μm , respectively at detector distance 776.8mm, the X-ray source wavelength was

$\lambda = 0.1348$ nm. Measurements were conducted at 20 °C in a 1 mm quartz capillary, at a q vector range from 0.047 to 4.4 nm⁻¹, where $q = 4\pi \cdot \sin\theta/\lambda$ is the length of the scattering vector and θ is one-half of the scattering angle. Data were collected for 30 min (60 frames by 30s). During the data reduction, the intensities were normalized to sample transmission and primary beam fluctuation, which was monitored using semi-transparent beamstop. SAXS curves were obtained by subtracting the solvent intensities from those for the sample. Data were modelled using the SasView 5.0.6 package.

Transmission electron microscopy (TEM) – this method was used to observe the morphology of copolymer nanoparticles. The measurements were performed in bright field mode using a Tecnai G2 Spirit Twin 120 kV TEM (FEI, Czech Republic) microscope. The nanoparticles were diluted in either hexane (DP1 < 18) or dodecane (DP1 > 18) to a concentration of 0.25 or 1 mg mL⁻¹, respectively, and were dropped on a copper TEM grid coated with a thin electron transparent carbon film. After 2 min, the excess solution was removed by touching the bottom of the grids with filtering paper to minimize oversaturation during the drying process. Dilution in hexane led to faster solvent evaporation and prevented the coalescence of worm-like nanoparticles. In this case, the particles were visible even without negative staining with uranyl acetate. Dilution by hexane instead of dodecane did not result in a significant change in nanoparticle DLS results (Figure S11). Additionally, the nanoparticles diluted in dodecane were negatively stained with uranyl acetate (2 wt.%) solution dropped on the dried nanoparticles and removed after 30 s, as described above). The samples were left to dry completely at room temperature and then observed on the microscope.

Matrix-assisted laser desorption/ionization-time of flight mass spectrometry (MALDI-TOF MS) was performed on a Microflex LT MALDI-TOF MS (Bruker Daltonics) mass spectrometer. All mass spectra were recorded at a 20 kV accelerating potential in positive ion and reflection modes (matrix: 2-[3-(4-tert-butylphenyl)-2-methyl-2-propenylidene] malononitrile (DCTB)). Samples were applied to the MALDI plate using the dried drop method. All measurements were calibrated using poly(ethylene glycol) monomethyl ether (mPEG, Mn = 2000 Da).

Preparation of Pickering emulsions – 20 μ L of Nile Red dispersion in dodecane (5 mg/mL) and distilled water were added to copolymer dispersions diluted in *n*-dodecane. The mixture was homogenized for 2 min at 20 °C using an IKA Ultra-Turrax T-18 homogenizer with a 10 mm

dispersing tool operating at 12 000 rpm. The water/dodecane volume ratio was kept at 10/90 and the copolymer weight concentration in the mixture was changed between 2.00-0.25% w/w by progressive dilution.

Optical microscopy – Optical microscopy images of Pickering emulsion droplets were recorded using a Motic BA210 digital biological microscope equipped with a built-in camera and analyzed using Motic Images Plus 2.0 ML software in epifluorescent mode.

Kinetic Monte Carlo simulation code

The following simplified VBA code for visualization of repeating distribution units in copolymers was used as a macro in Microsoft Excel software. The simulation has been performed for 10 chains on ([EHOx]:[PhOx]:[MeOTs] = 63:27:1 statistical copolymerization with reactivity ratios $r_{\text{EHOx}} = 8.03$, $r_{\text{PhOx}} = 0.10$

```
Sub CopolymerizationSimulation()  
    Dim rA As Double  
    Dim rB As Double  
    rA = 2.07 ' Reactivity ratio of monomer A  
    rB = 0.16 ' Reactivity ratio of monomer B  
  
    Dim amountA As Double  
    Dim amountB As Double  
    amountA = 50  
    amountB = 200  
  
    Dim chainLength As Integer  
    chainLength = 250  
  
    Dim numSimulations As Integer  
    numSimulations = 100  
  
    Dim ws As Worksheet  
    Set ws = ThisWorkbook.Sheets("Sheet1")  
    ws.Cells.Clear  
  
    Randomize  
  
    Dim sim As Integer, unit As Integer  
    Dim currentAmountA As Double, currentAmountB As Double  
    Dim totalAmount As Double, moleFractionA As Double, moleFractionB As  
Double  
    Dim randNum As Double, probA As Double, probB As Double
```

```

Dim lastMonomer As String

For sim = 1 To numSimulations
    currentAmountA = amountA
    currentAmountB = amountB
    lastMonomer = "A"

    For unit = 1 To chainLength
        totalAmount = currentAmountA + currentAmountB
        moleFractionA = currentAmountA / totalAmount
        moleFractionB = currentAmountB / totalAmount

        randNum = Rnd

        If lastMonomer = "A" Then
            probA = (rA * moleFractionA) / (rA * moleFractionA +
moleFractionB)
            probB = 1 - probA
        Else
            probB = (rB * moleFractionB) / (rB * moleFractionB +
moleFractionA)
            probA = 1 - probB
        End If

        If randNum < probA And currentAmountA > 0 Then
            ws.Cells(sim, unit).Value = "A"
            lastMonomer = "A"
            currentAmountA = currentAmountA - 1
        ElseIf currentAmountB > 0 Then
            ws.Cells(sim, unit).Value = "B"
            lastMonomer = "B"
            currentAmountB = currentAmountB - 1
        End If
    Next unit
Next sim
End Sub

```


Figure S1. PPhOx precipitated on the walls of the reaction vial from the reaction crude of the homopolymerization in *n*-dodecane.

Figure S2. Hydrodynamic diameters as derived from DLS measurements for PEHO_{x18}-*b*-PPhO_{x60} block copolymer at different conversions of the PhOx block in dodecane.

Table S1. Hydrodynamic diameters (D_h) and polydispersities (PDI) measured by DLS for different copolymer compositions, architectures and total solid weight concentrations.

Polymer	Concentration (w/w %)	D_h (nm)	PDI
PEHO _{X17.5} - <i>b</i> -PPhO _{X27}	15	40.2	0.156
PEHO _{X17.5} - <i>b</i> -PPhO _{X32}	15	90.5	0.286
PEHO _{X17.5} - <i>b</i> -PPhO _{X40}	15	54.2	0.088
PEHO _{X17.5} - <i>b</i> -PPhO _{X45}	20	NS	NS
PEHO _{X17.5} - <i>b</i> -PPhO _{X52}	20	NS	NS
PEHO _{X17.5} - <i>b</i> -PPhO _{X70}	20	72.1	0.084
PEHO _{X15.5} - <i>b</i> -PPhO _{X22}	25	45.9	0.194
PEHO _{X15.5} - <i>b</i> -PPhO _{X29}	25	NS	NS
PEHO _{X15.5} - <i>b</i> -PPhO _{X33}	25	NS	NS
PEHO _{X15.5} - <i>b</i> -PPhO _{X34}	25	NS	NS
PEHO _{X16} - <i>b</i> -PPhO _{X24}	25	50.9	0.249
PEHO _{X16} - <i>b</i> -PPhO _{X34}	25	NS	NS
PEHO _{X16} - <i>b</i> -PPhO _{X41}	25	NS	NS
PEHO _{X16.5} - <i>b</i> -PPhO _{X16}	25	19.0	0.070
PEHO _{X16.5} - <i>b</i> -PPhO _{X26}	25	73.9	0.245
PEHO _{X16.5} - <i>b</i> -PPhO _{X32}	25	87.7	0.369
PEHO _{X16.5} - <i>b</i> -PPhO _{X56}	25	69.6	0.113
PEHO _{X17.5} - <i>b</i> -PPhO _{X13}	25	18.1	0.117
PEHO _{X17.5} - <i>b</i> -PPhO _{X30}	25	81.2	0.247
PEHO _{X17.5} - <i>b</i> -PPhO _{X32}	25	58.9	0.152
PEHO _{X17.5} - <i>b</i> -PPhO _{X49}	25	31.5	0.022
PEHO _{X18} - <i>b</i> -PPhO _{X23}	25	30.9	0.256
PEHO _{X18} - <i>b</i> -PPhO _{X37}	25	50.0	0.166
PEHO _{X18} - <i>b</i> -PPhO _{X44}	25	42.4	0.114
PEHO _{X18} - <i>b</i> -PPhO _{X57}	25	42.4	0.065
PEHO _{X20} - <i>b</i> -PPhO _{X21}	25	18.9	0.056
PEHO _{X20} - <i>b</i> -PPhO _{X29}	25	28.1	0.078
PEHO _{X20} - <i>b</i> -PPhO _{X44}	25	30.6	0.065
PEHO _{X20} - <i>b</i> -PPhO _{X51}	25	36.6	0.099
PEHO _{X20} - <i>b</i> -PPhO _{X85}	25	48.6	0.055
PEHO _{X20} - <i>b</i> -PPhO _{X96}	25	49.8	0.056
PEHO _{X20} - <i>b</i> -PPhO _{X101}	25	51.6	0.057
PEHO _{X20} - <i>b</i> -PPhO _{X153}	25	69.5	0.050
PEHO _{X22.5} - <i>b</i> -PPhO _{X53}	25	31.7	0.058
PEHO _{X22.5} - <i>b</i> -PPhO _{X56}	25	32.1	0.055
PEHO _{X22.5} - <i>b</i> -PPhO _{X58}	25	35.0	0.052
PEHO _{X22.5} - <i>b</i> -PPhO _{X68}	25	38.0	0.058
PEHO _{X22.5} - <i>b</i> -PPhO _{X180}	25	83.8	0.040
PEHO _{X22.5} - <i>b</i> -PPhO _{X210}	25	93.8	0.094
PEHO _{X17.5} - <i>b</i> -PPhO _{X15}	40	16.4	0.083
PEHO _{X17.5} - <i>b</i> -PPhO _{X24}	40	75.8	0.335

PEHO _X _{17.5} - <i>b</i> -PPhO _X ₃₉	40	NS	NS
PEHO _X _{17.5} - <i>b</i> -PPhO _X ₄₇	40	NS	NS
PEHO _X ₃₈ - <i>g</i> -PPhO _X ₁₆	25	17.3	0.126
PEHO _X ₃₈ - <i>g</i> -PPhO _X ₃₀	25	40.5	0.198
PEHO _X ₃₈ - <i>g</i> -PPhO _X ₄₇	25	NS	NS
PEHO _X ₃₈ - <i>g</i> -PPhO _X ₆₉	25	NS	NS

NS: sample not soluble in dodecane

Figure S3. PEHO_X₁₈ synthesized in dodecane. ¹H NMR spectrum acquired in CDCl₃ (left). MALDI-ToF spectrum of the water-terminated polymer (right).

Figure S4. TEM micrographs of PEHO_{x22.5}-*b*-PPhO_{x210} nanoparticles synthesized at 25 % w/w (diluted to 1 mg mL⁻¹ in dodecane).

Figure S5. Phase diagram of PEHO_{x17.5}-*b*-PPhO_{xm} copolymer nanoparticles prepared by CROPISA in dodecane at different total solid weight concentrations. A one-pot protocol was employed to synthesize all the block copolymers.

Figure S6. Hydrodynamic diameters as derived from DLS measurements for PEHOx₆₃-*b*-PPhOx₂₇ gradient copolymer synthesis at different polymerization times in dodecane.

Figure S7. Semilogarithmic plot of conversion over time for the copolymerization of EHOx and PhOx in acetonitrile at 140 °C, [EHOx]:[PhOx]:[MeOTs] = 52:42:1, monomer concentration 26 wt. %

Figure S8. Meyer-Lowry plot of the copolymerization of EHOx and PhOx in dodecane at 140 °C, [EHOx]:[PhOx]:[MeOTs] = 63:27:1, monomer concentration 25 wt.%. The reactivity ratios for EHOx (r_E) and PhOx (r_P) were derived as parameters from the fitting function.

Figure S9. RI and UV SEC traces of PEHOx₄₄-b-PPhOx₃₈ copolymer synthesized in dodecane by a PISA protocol at 140 °C (second block). The higher content of the UV-absorbing PPhOx monomer in the low molecular weight shoulder is highlighted by the comparison with the IR trace.

Figure S10. Mean droplet diameters *versus* copolymer concentration (left) and representative optical microscope images (right) for emulsions stabilized by PEHO_{X15.5}-*b*-PPhO_{X22} (worms) and PEHO_{X20}-*b*-PPhO_{X101} (spheres).

Figure S11. Hydrodynamic diameter distributions of PEHO_{x16.5}-b-PPhO_{x26} and PEHO_{x16.5}-b-PPhO_{x32} nanoparticles diluted in *n*-dodecane and hexane measured by DLS.

T14

T15

T16

Figure S12. PEHO_{x_n} and PEHO_{x_n}-*b*-PPhO_{x_m} copolymers synthesized in dodecane by CROPISA. ¹H NMR spectra acquired in CDCl₃ or CD₂Cl₂ (left). SEC traces of copolymers in DMAc eluent (right).